

РАЗДЕЛ. ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫЕ НАУКИ

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15364427>

UDK 52-17

**MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF THE STRESS STATE
OF A RING-SHAPED REGION UNDER INTERNAL PRESSURE**

Le Thi Hong Van*, **Nguyen Minh Hue**,
Ho Chi Minh City University of Transport,
Ho Chi Minh City
*Corresponding authors

Annotation: In this study, mathematical modeling of the elastoplastic state of a cylindrical region under internal pressure is performed. The problem is considered within the approximation of plane stress conditions. The results provide insight into the stress-strain behavior of the material.

Keywords: elastoplastic state, internal pressure, stress-strain behavior

**МАТЕМАТИЧЕСКОЕ МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ
НАПРЯЖЕННОГО СОСТОЯНИЯ КОЛЬЦЕВОЙ ОБЛАСТИ
ПОД ВНУТРЕННИМ ДАВЛЕНИЕМ**

Ле Тхи Хонг Ван*, **Нгуен Минь Хюэ**,
Университет транспорта города Хошимин,
Хошимин
*Авторы-корреспонденты

Аннотация: В данном исследовании выполнено математическое моделирование упругопластического состояния цилиндрической области под внутренним давлением. Задача рассматривается в приближении условий плоского напряжения. Результаты дают представление о напряженно-деформированном состоянии материала.

Ключевые слова: упругопластическое состояние, внутреннее давление, напряженно-деформированное состояние

1. The Onset of the Plastic Zone

Let us choose a yield criterion of the form (r, θ, z – cylindrical coordinate system).

$$\max\{|2\sigma_r - \sigma_\theta - \sigma_z|, |2\sigma_\theta - \sigma_r - \sigma_z|, |2\sigma_z - \sigma_\theta - \sigma_r|\} = 2k \quad (1)$$

A pressure p is applied to the inner boundary of the region $R_i \leq r \leq R_e$.

Since the radial stress in the plastic region is determined from the solution of the Cauchy problem, and considering the plasticity hexagon defined by equation (1), it can be observed that:

– for $0 < p \leq \frac{2k}{3}$, the plastic region may exhibit the plasticity condition:

$$2\sigma_\theta - \sigma_r = 2k \quad (2)$$

– for $\frac{2k}{3} < p \leq \frac{4k}{3}$, two plasticity conditions may be realized:

$$2\sigma_\theta - \sigma_r = 2k \text{ and } 2\sigma_r - \sigma_\theta = -2k. \quad (3)$$

The contact pressure p cannot exceed $\frac{4k}{3}$, as this would correspond to the stress vector exceeding the plasticity surface limit at the contact boundary of the disks.

The minimum contact pressure at which the plasticity condition (2) is satisfied at the boundary $r = R_i$ is determined from the solution of the problem for a cylindrical region in an elastic state [1]:

$$p = \frac{k}{2} \frac{R_e^2 - R_i^2}{3R_e^2 + R_i^2}.$$

2. Stresses in the Plastic Region

We will denote the radius of the elastic-plastic boundary as c . If

$$\frac{k}{2} \frac{R_e^2 - R_i^2}{3R_e^2 + R_i^2} \leq p \leq \frac{2k}{3}, \quad (4)$$

then in the plastic region $R_i \leq r \leq c$, the stress state is determined from the solution of the Cauchy problem:

$$\begin{cases} 2\sigma_\theta - \sigma_r = 2k \\ \frac{d}{dr}(r\sigma_r) - \sigma_\theta = 0 \\ \sigma_r|_{r=R_i} = -p \end{cases}$$

Solving these equations, the stresses in the plastic region are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_r &= 2k - (p + 2k)\sqrt{\frac{R_i}{r}}, \\ \sigma_\theta &= 2k - \frac{1}{2}(p + 2k)\sqrt{\frac{R_i}{r}}. \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

The limiting state in the disk occurs when the contact pressure varies within the range (4), provided that the outer radius of the second disk is given by:

$$R_e = \frac{(p+2k)^2 R_i}{4k^2}. \tag{6}$$

From equation (6), the maximum radius R_e for which only the plasticity condition (2) can be realized in the plastic region is determined as:

$$R_e = \frac{16}{9} R.$$

3. Deformations and displacements in the plastic region

In the plastic region, the deformations include both elastic and plastic components:

$$\varepsilon_r = \frac{du}{dr} = \varepsilon_r^e + \varepsilon_r^p, \quad \varepsilon_\theta = \frac{u}{r} \varepsilon_\theta^e + \varepsilon_\theta^p. \tag{7}$$

The elastic strains are expressed in terms of stresses using Hooke's law:

$$E\varepsilon_r^e = \sigma_r - \nu\sigma_\theta, \quad E\varepsilon_\theta^e = \sigma_\theta - \nu\sigma_r.$$

Here, E is the Young's modulus, and ν is the Poisson's ratio. Considering relations (7) and formulas (6), the elastic strains are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} E\varepsilon_r^e &= 2k(1 - \nu) - \frac{(2-\nu)(p-2k)}{2} \sqrt{\frac{R_i}{r}}, \\ E\varepsilon_\theta^e &= 2k(1 - \nu) - \frac{(1-2\nu)(p-2k)}{2} \sqrt{\frac{R_i}{r}}. \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Within the framework of the natural state hypothesis, based on the associated flow rule corresponding to condition (2), the following equality holds:

$$\varepsilon_\theta^p - 2\varepsilon_r^p = 0. \tag{9}$$

By eliminating the elastic and plastic strains from equations (7)–(9) and considering that plastic strains are zero at the elastic-plastic boundary

($\varepsilon_{\theta}^p|_{r=c} = \varepsilon_r^p|_{r=c} = 0$), the displacement in the plastic region is determined from the following problem:

$$\begin{cases} 2 \frac{dEu}{dr} + \frac{Eu}{r} = 6k(1-\nu) + \left(2\nu - \frac{5}{2}\right)(p+2k)\sqrt{\frac{R_i}{r}}, \\ \left(\frac{Eu}{r} - \sigma_{\theta} + \nu\sigma_r\right)|_{r=c} = 0. \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

The solution to problem (10) has the form:

$$Ee_r = 2k(1-\nu)r + \sqrt{a}(p+2k)\left(\frac{3}{4}\frac{c_2}{r} + \nu - \frac{5}{4}\right)\sqrt{r}.$$

According to equation (7), the strains are given by:

$$Ee_r = 2k(1-\nu) + \frac{1}{2}(p+2k)\left(\nu - \frac{5}{4} - \frac{3}{4}\frac{c_2}{r}\right)\sqrt{\frac{a}{r}},$$

$$Ee_{\theta} = 2k(1-\nu) + (p+2k)\left(\nu - \frac{5}{4} + \frac{3}{4}\frac{c_2}{r}\right)\sqrt{\frac{a}{r}}.$$

The plastic deformations are given by:

$$Ee_r^p = \frac{3}{8}(p+2k)\left(1 - \frac{c_2}{r}\right)\sqrt{\frac{a}{r}},$$

$$Ee_{\theta}^p = \frac{3}{4}(p+2k)\left(\frac{c_2}{r} - 1\right)\sqrt{\frac{a}{r}}.$$

4. Stresses, deformations, and displacements in the elastic region

At the elastic-plastic boundary, the stresses are continuous. On the outer boundary of the second disk, the radial stress satisfies the condition:

$$\sigma_r|_{r=R_e} = 0.$$

Therefore, the radial component of the stress tensor in the elastic region of the disk $c \leq r \leq R_e$ can be determined either from the boundary value problem or from the Cauchy problem solution.

We choose the following boundary value problem:

$$\begin{cases} r^2 \frac{d^2\sigma_r}{dr^2} + 3r \frac{d\sigma_r}{dr} = 0, \\ \sigma_r|_{r=R_e} = 0, \\ \left(2 \frac{dr\sigma_r}{dr} - \sigma_r\right)|_{r=c} = 2k. \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

The condition at the elastic-plastic boundary $r = c$ follows from the continuity of stresses at this interface. The solution to problem (11) is:

$$\sigma_r = -\frac{2kc^2}{3R_e^2+c^2}\left(\frac{R_e^2}{r^2} - 1\right), \quad \sigma_{\theta} = \frac{2kc^2}{3R_e^2+c^2}\left(\frac{R_e^2}{r^2} + 1\right). \quad (12)$$

Depending on the chosen boundary conditions for determining the stresses in the elastic region, the formulas in (12) may take a different form but can be transformed into (12).

From the condition of stress continuity at the elastic-plastic boundary, the equation for determining the radius of the elastic-plastic boundary is given by:

$$(2k + p) \sqrt{\frac{R_i}{c}} - \frac{8kR_e^2}{3R_e^2 + c^2} = 0.$$

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figures 1-3 show the distribution of stresses, plastic deformations, and displacements for the following values of dimensionless parameters: $R_i = 1$, $R_e = 1.5$, $p = 0.4$, $\nu = 0.2$.

The issues of mathematical modeling of the elastoplastic state of cylindrical regions using piecewise-linear plasticity conditions in the plane strain approximation have been considered, for example, in studies [2-9].

Bibliography

- [1] Darkov A.V. Strength of Materials. / A.V. Darkov, G.S. Shapiro – Moscow: Higher School, 1965. 762 p.
- [2] Alexandrov A.V. Strength of Materials. / A.V. Alexandrov, V.D. Potapov, B.P. Derzhavin – Moscow: Vysshaya Shkola, 2000. 560 p.
- [3] Artemov M.A. Alternative Forms of Piecewise-Linear Plasticity Conditions and Their Generalizations. / M.A. Artemov, E.S. Baranovsky, A.P. Yakubenko // Bulletin of Voronezh State University. Series: Physics. Mathematics. – 2015. No. 1. 71-82 p.
- [4] Artemov M.A. Isotropy Relations and the Associated Flow Rule. / M.A. Artemov, E.S. Baranovsky, A.P. Yakubenko // Bulletin of Voronezh State University. Series: Physics. Mathematics. – 2014. No. 4. 81-90 p.
- [5] Artemov M.A. Mathematical Modeling of the Equilibrium State of a Circular Cylindrical Pipe. / M.A. Artemov, N.S. Potapov, A.P.

Yakubenko // Bulletin of Voronezh State Technical University. – 2011. Vol. 7. No. 5. 126-128 p.

[6] Artemov M.A. Mathematical Modeling of the Plastic State of Bodies: Plane Strain Deformation. / M.A. Artemov, E.S. Baranovsky // Bulletin of I. Ya. Yakovlev Chuvash State Pedagogical University. Series: Mechanics of the Limit State. – 2015. No. 2 (24). 72-87 p.

[7] Artemov M.A. On the Relations Derived from the Maximum Equivalent Stress Plasticity Condition. / M.A. Artemov, N.S. Potapov, A.P. Yakubenko // Bulletin of Voronezh State Technical University. – 2011. Vol. 7. No. 4. 4-5 p.

[8] Artemov M.A. On the Relations Derived from Tresca's Plasticity Condition. / M.A. Artemov, N.S. Potapov, A.P. Yakubenko // Bulletin of Voronezh State Technical University. – 2011. Vol. 7. No. 3. 7-8 p.

[9] Artemov M.A. Limit Conditions of Plasticity. / M.A. Artemov, E.S. Baranovsky, A.P. Yakubenko // Theoretical and Applied Issues of Education and Science: Collection of Scientific Papers from the International Scientific and Practical Conference. – Tambov, 2014. 13-14 p.

Список литературы (перевод)

[1] Дарков А.В. Сопrotивление материалов. / А.В. Дарков, Г.С. Шапиро – М.: Высшая школа, 1965. 762 с.

[2] Александров А.В. Сопrotивление материалов. / А.В. Александров, В.Д. Потапов, Б.П. Державин – М.: Высшая школа, 2000. 560 с.

[3] Артемов М.А. Альтернативные формы кусочно-линейных условий пластичности и их обобщения. / М.А. Артемов, Е.С. Барановский, А.П. Якубенко // Вестник Воронежского государственного университета. Серия: Физика. Математика. – 2015. № 1. 71-82 с.

[4] Артемов М.А. Соотношения изотропии и ассоциированное с ними правило течения. / М.А. Артемов, Е.С. Барановский, А.П. Якубенко // Вестник Воронежского государственного университета. Серия: Физика. Математика. – 2014. № 4. 81-90 с.

[5] Артемов М.А. Математическое моделирование равновесного состояния круглой цилиндрической трубы. / М.А. Артемов, Н.С.

Потапов, А.П. Якубенко // Вестник Воронежского государственного технического университета. – 2011. Т. 7. № 5. 126-128 с.

[6] Артемов М.А. Математическое моделирование пластического состояния тел: плоская деформация. / М.А. Артемов, Е.С. Барановский // Вестник Чувашского государственного педагогического университета им. И.Я. Яковлева. Серия: Механика предельного состояния. – 2015. № 2 (24). 72-87 с.

[7] Артемов М.А. О соотношениях, выводимых из условия пластичности по максимальному эквивалентному напряжению. / М.А. Артемов, Н.С. Потапов, А.П. Якубенко // Известия Воронежского государственного технического университета. – 2011. Т. 7. № 4. 4-5 с.

[8] Артемов М.А. О соотношениях, выводимых из условия пластичности Треска. / М.А. Артемов, Н.С. Потапов, А.П. Якубенко // Известия Воронежского государственного технического университета. – 2011. Т. 7. № 3. 7-8 с.

[9] Артемов М.А. Предельные условия пластичности. / М.А. Артемов, Е.С. Барановский, А.П. Якубенко // Теоретические и прикладные проблемы образования и науки: Сборник научных трудов Международной научно-практической конференции. – Тамбов, 2014. – 13–14 с.

© *Le Thi Hong Van, Nguyen Minh Hue, 2025*

Поступила в редакцию 8.03.2025
Принята к публикации 27.03.2025

Для цитирования:

Le Thi Hong Van, Nguyen Minh Hue Mathematical modeling of the stress state of a ring-shaped region under internal pressure // Инновационные научные исследования. 2025. № 3-2(56). С. 4-11. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>